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Psychological Traits Influencing Mental Health and Well-being Amongst Differently Abled Adolescents

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar**

The present study was conducted on 100 female disabled adolescents to assess their mental health behaviour and well-being in terms of their coping strategies behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation. It was hypothesized that mental health behaviour and well-being of female disabled adolescents will be significantly associated with their coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation, (ii) Psychological traits under study will be found significantly related. For the purpose, the adolescents were administered MHB by Sen-Gupta and Singh, Coping Strategies Scale by Folkman and Lazarus, Behavioural Pattern Scale by Dhar and Jain and Masculinity-Femininity Check List by Sinha to measure mental health, coping strategies, behavioural pattern, androgyny and sex-typed traits respectively. Besides these, PDS was administered to them to seek the necessary information about them. The obtained data were analysed and treated using chi-square and Pearsonian 'r'. The results confirmed the hypotheses. It was found that differently abled adolescents belonging to problem focused coping strategy group, type 'B' behavioural pattern group and androgyny group excelled over their counterpart groups i.e. emotion focused group, type 'A' behavioural pattern group and sex-typed trait group of disabled adolescents in terms of having sound mental health behaviour. Mental health behaviour was found significantly correlated with coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation. Thus, it is concluded that problem focused coping strategy, type B behavioural pattern and androgyny are conducive to sound mental health behavioural.

Introduction

The present study embodies four components which need elaboration. The first component is mental health behaviour which refers to behaviour based on mental health index. Mental health is an index which shows the extent to which the person has been able to meet his environment demands - social, emotional and physical. However, when he/she finds himself/herself trapped in a situation he does not have matching coping strategies to deal with it effectively, he/she gets himself/herself mentally strained. This mental strain is generally reflected in symptoms like anxiety, tension, restlessness or hopelessness among others. If it is felt for too long and too extensively by the person, these symptoms may take a definite form, representing a given illness. Mental health, therefore, should not be confused with mental illness, it is a study of pre-illness mental condition of the person (Kumar, 1991). Mental health, as such, represents a psychic condition which is characterized by mental peace, harmony and content. It is identified by the absence of disabling and debilitating symptoms, both mental and somatic in the person (Schneider's, 1964).

Coping strategies are actions that persons can take to reduce or minimise the effects of stressors. People often use three types of coping strategies - (i) Problem focused coping (attempt to eliminate or change the stressor or itself), (ii) Emotional focused coping (changing the ways of feelings or emotional reactions to the stressors) and (iii) Seeking social support. In the present study the first two coping strategies will be undertaken.

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Other personality components of the present study is type A/B - behavioural pattern which needs elaboration. Type A-behaviour pattern is characterised by greater degree of competitiveness oriented, unrealistic parental aspiration etc. Type A people are work alcoholics, continuously striving to get more in less time. Such people can not tolerate being looked down upon. Besides these, resentment frequent anger, suspiciousness, distrust and antagonism are also the basic characteristics of type-A behavioural pattern. Contrary to it type-B behaviour pattern is characterised by complacently, easy going, non-assertive, relaxed and patience.

Next component is sex-role orientation which needs elaboration. Sex-role orientation embodies the concept of masculinity, femininity and androgyny. So, psychological androgyny is the presence of both masculinity and femininity. In term masculinity and femininity are defined as additive combination of trait term judge to be significantly more desirable for, or more characteristics of, each sex relative to other. Androgyny is personality which holds a balance of feminine and masculine characteristics. An androgynous person would be one comfortable with displaying both characteristics and able to move back and forth between the two.

A review of literature reveals that personality factors like poor emotional-stability, poor ego-strength, poor decision-making abilities coupled with a lack of sense of responsibility as well as negative self-concept are often associated with poor quality of mental health behaviour- Chatterjee, Mukherjee & Chakaraborty 1980). Poor degree of emotional stability causes a sense of emotional imbalance and if it continues for a longer period of time, it is likely to have an impact upon the cognitive functioning, thereby, influencing the mental health behaviour of the persons. Students who have to face various types of problems in their academic career often demonstrate poor emotional-stability and ultimately to poor mental health behaviour. Ego-strength is also a factor that tends to influence mental health behaviour. Generally, persons with high ego-strength have greater self-confidence and self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is the belief that one can perform the behaviours necessary to cope successfully. Following Bandura (1997), self-efficacy is an important protective factor. Feeling of self-efficacy may fortify our bodies as well as mind against stressful event and may improve mental health (Suls and Wallston, 2003). When subjects reported high degree of self-efficacy while confronting the stressful situation, their immune system actually begins to function more effectively. Likewise, decision-making quality is also a factor that affects mental health behaviour. It has been reported that persons equipped with high decision-making quality have generally better cognitive functioning than persons having poor decision-making quality. Such persons in their day- today dealing tend to display evidences for developed cognitive functioning. They take a decision, enjoy it and remove many types of mental conflict, resulting in improved mental health behaviour. Recent evidences often support the fact that some people are self-healers who are able to function effectively even in case of intense ongoing stress [Carver et al. (1993)]. Kirti (2008) found that mental health is a function of aggression, anxiety and adjustment. Kobasa et al. (1982) found stress, hardiness and health are inter-correlated. Kumar D. (2012) reported that mental health is a function of androgyny and emotional adjustment Kumar (2012) found that mental health is the function of parental style and life satisfaction, Kumar, (2011) reported that emotional maturity and adjustment are positively correlated, Mishra (2012) found that level of aspiration, mental health and adjustment were found significantly correlated. Plancherel et al. (1995) reported that coping and mental health are significantly and positively correlated. Schneiders (1964) stated that personal development and mental health are significantly correlated Taurab (2009) found that

personality factors and mental health are significantly correlated. Tickoo (2006) found that introversion and mental health are significantly correlated. Vander Voort et al. (2007) found that locus of control and mental health are significantly correlated.

It is clear from the results that mental health have been studied in context of several psychological traits but without including coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation especially in the context of Patna, Bihar, This justifies undertaking of the study.

Objectives

The study intends to examine the association of coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation with mental health behaviour amongst disabled. Further, it was intended to examine the relationship of mental health with variables (coping strategies, personality pattern and sex-role orientation.)

Hypotheses

- (1) There will be significant association of coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation with mental health behaviour amongst disabled.
- (2) There will be significant relationship of mental health with coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation.

Method of Study

Design Employed

The proposal embodying the sole dependent variable i.e. mental health behaviour and three independent variables namely coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation as independent variables. Respondents were grouped into problem focused coping strategy group, emotional focused coping strategy group, type-A behavioural pattern group, type-B behavioural pattern group, sex-typed trait group and androgynous group. Each independent variable group comprised of independent subjects, therefore, between group design was preferred.

Sample Used

The sample comprised of 100 orthopedically disabled female adolescents (14–18 yrs.) selected from among different rehabilitation centres of Patna using incidental-cum purposive sampling technique. Other than the conditions required for research the subjects were matched so far as practicable.

Tools Used

- A Personal Data Sheet was used to seek the necessary information about the orthopedically disabled to be used as sample in the present study.
- Mental Health Battery by Singh, A.K. and Sen Gupta, A was used to measure mental health behaviour of the respondent.
- Type A/B Behavioural Pattern Scale by Dhar, Upindra and Jain, Manisha was used to measure behavioural pattern of the respondents.
- Masculinity-Femininity Check List by Sinha, T.N. was used to identify the sex-role orientation i.e. sex-typed traits and androgyny.
- Coping Strategies Scale by Folkman and Lazarus was used to measure coping strategy of disabled adolescents.

Administration of Scales for Data Collection

The scales along with PDS were administered on the orthopedically disabled adolescents selected as sample. The respondents were grouped into problem focused Vs emotion focused coping strategies groups, type A Vs type B behavioural pattern groups and sex-typed Vs androgynous groups. The groups were formed as per direction of the manual. The mental health behaviour of orthopedically disabled adolescents belonging to six different

groups were compared using chi-square. The relationship amongst the variables were examined using Pearsonian 'r'. The results have been displayed in table-1 and 2 respectively as under.

Results

Table - 1

Chi-square showing association of coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation with mental health behaviour amongst orthopedically disabled adolescents.

Variable	Groups	N	Mental Health Behaviour		χ^2	df	p
			Sound	Poor			
Coping Strategies	Problem Focused	38	70% (N=27)	30% (N=11)	18.18	1	<.01
	Emotional Focused	62	40% (N = 25)	60% (N=37)			
	A/B Behavioural pattern	Type-'A'	66	36% (N=24)			
	Type-'B'	34	70% (N=24)	30% (N=10)			
Sex-role orientation	Sex-typed	70	34% (N=24)	66% (N=76)	29.17	1	<.01
	Androgynous	30	72% (N=22)	28% (N=08)			

The results displayed by table-1 clearly revealed that coping strategies have significant association with mental health behaviour amongst disabled adolescents. It was found that more than 70% (N = 27) respondents belonging to problem focused coping strategy group manifested sound mental health behaviour whereas only 30% (N = 11) of disabled adolescents manifested poor mental health behaviour. On the other hand only 40% (N = 25) of respondents belonging to emotion focused coping strategy group manifested sound mental health behaviour and more than 60% (N = 37) of this group manifested poor mental health behaviour. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 18.18$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus hypothesis no. (1) is partly retained.

Further, more than 70% (N = 24) of disabled adolescents belongings to type-'B' behavioural pattern group and only 36% (N = 24) of disabled adolescents of type-'A' behavioural pattern group manifested sound mental health behaviour. On the other hand more than 66% (N = 42) of disabled adolescents of type-'A' behavioural pattern group and only 30% (N = 10) of disabled of type-'B' behavioural pattern group manifested poor mental health behaviour. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 24.75$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (1) again is retained partly.

Finally, more than 72% (N = 22) of androgynous trait group of disabled adolescents and only 34% (N = 24) of sex-typed group of disabled adolescents manifested sound mental health behaviour. On the other hand, more than 66% (N = 56) of disabled adolescents belonging to sex-typed trait groups manifested poor mental health behaviour. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 29.17$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (1) is fully retained.

The findings of results of table-01 might be interpreted on the ground that (i) disabled adolescents belonging to problem focused coping strategy group are more concerned with nature and severity of problem than the emotion, (ii) The disabled respondents

belonging to type-'B' behavioural pattern group are characterised by easy going, less stressed and relaxed mood and (iii) The disabled adolescents belonging to androgynous group are more confident, and having the ability to face the problems before them, leading to excel in terms of manifesting sound mental health behaviour as compared to their counterpart groups of respondents.

Table-2

Pearsonian 'r' showing co-efficient of correlation of coping strategies, A/B behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation with mental health behaviour (MHB).

Variables	N	r	df	p
Problem Focus Coping Strategy Vs MHB	38	0.392	36	<.01
Emotion Focused Coping Strategy Vs MHB	62	-0.368	60	<.01
Type 'A' Behavioural Pattern Vs MHB	66	-0.413	62	<.01
Type 'B' Vs MHB	34	0.439	32	<.01
Sex-Typed Traits Vs MHB	70	-0.385	68	<.01
Androgynous Traits Vs MHB	30	0.440	28	<.01

The results displayed by table-2 clearly revealed that there exist a significant positive correlation of problems focused coping strategy Vs MHB ($r = 0.392$; $df = 36$; $p < .01$); type 'B' behavioural pattern Vs MHB ($r = 0.439$; $df = 32$; $p < .01$) and between androgynous trait vs MHB ($r = 0.440$; $df = 36$; $p < .01$). On the other hand there exists a significant negative correlation between emotion focused coping strategy vs MHB ($r = -0.368$; $df = 36$; $p < .01$); between type 'A' Behavioural Pattern Vs MHB ($r = -0.413$; $df = 64$; $p < .01$); and between sex-typed traits vs MHB ($r = -0.385$; $df = 68$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (2) is retained. The findings are in agreement with the findings of table - (1), Interpretation remained the same.

Conclusions

- (1) Mental health behaviour among disabled adolescents is a function of coping strategies, type A/B behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation. The disabled adolescents belonging to problem focused coping strategy group, type 'B' behavioural pattern group and androgynous trait group excelled over their counterparts in terms of having sound mental health behaviour.
- (2) Coping strategies, behavioural pattern and sex-role orientation have significant relationship with mental health behaviour.

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